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**BRIEF DATA ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL
ASPECTS AND HUMAN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES: SMES
VILLAVICENCIO**

¹Dagoberto Torres-Flórez,²Hernando Castro-Garzón,³Jhon Jairo Feria-Díaz

^{1,2} Profesor escuela de Administración y Negocios. Universidad de los Llanos.
Villavicencio, Colombia.

³Profesor Titular. Facultad de Ingeniería. Universidad de Sucre. Sincelejo, Colombia.

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Data On The Relationship Between Organizational Aspects And Human Management
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**Keywords: Organizational development, human resources, SMEs, Villavicencio,
human management.**

ABSTRACT:

The data presented allows us to know the relationship between organizational aspects and human management practices. Data were separated by gender, age, salary, experience and educational level to enrich the information. Data was collected with the human talent managers of SMEs in Villavicencio, Meta-Colombia. A questionnaire (Mp10) was used, collecting a sample of 176 respondents. The descriptive statistics, Chi-square test and Pearson correlation were used to analyze the data. The information reflects that there are no significant differences in organizational development by gender, it was found as a dominant element to keep the manual of functions and procedures updated according to the needs of the business, as well as a significant relationship of the elements of the organizational aspects with the practices of human management.

Specifications Table:

SubjectArea	Management and business
More specificsubject área	Organizational Aspects of Human Management in SMEs.

Type of data	Tables
How data was acquired	The survey was carried out using a questionnaire (mp10). The instrument contains descriptive data of the respondents and a Likert scale questionnaire of 4 regarding the aspects of human management organizations.
Data format	Raw data, descriptive analysis and analyzed statistical data.
Description of data collection	Data were collected using Likert scale questionnaires of 4 for the organizational aspects and individual characteristics of the people responsible for the area with an accidental sampling method.
Data source location	Villavicencio, Meta-Colombia
Data accessibility	The data is included in this article.

Value of the data:

The data in this article shows a brief exploration of the application of the organizational aspects of human talent.[3]

The data set describes the difference in organizational aspects according to the gender[6], age[4], salary[2], experience[5] and educational level[1] of those responsible for human talent[7].

The data add value to future research on organizational aspects, work environment, organizational culture, job description and analysis, competency models and their relationship with human management practices.

For researchers studying SMEs, this data set provides valuable information to predict how those responsible for human talent influence organizational aspects and human management practices.

The data can be analyzed with other statistical techniques.

This data generates value in organizations to improve organizational development in the integration of people to improve the performance of collaborators.

1. Data:

The data is part of the study of measurement of human management practices carried out on people responsible for the area in SME companies in the city of Villavicencio. Research has shown that organizational aspects have impacts on human management practices and demographic and labor elements contribute to differences in the development of companies.

Once the elements of the organizational aspects are identified, they are chosen by characteristics such as gender, age, salary, experience and educational level to visualize the data and their differences.

Tables 1 and 2 present the organizational aspects regarding the demographics and job characteristics of the respondents. The Chi Square value and its significance were used to identify differences by group.

For advanced analysis, Pearson's correlation was used to identify the relationship between organizational aspects and human management practices (Table 6). Table 6 indicates that when organizational aspects are developed in SMEs, human management practices have a positive result.

Table 1: Perception of the person in charge of human talent by age and gender regarding organizational aspects.

Organizational aspect	The person in charge of human talent			
	Gender		Age	
	Chi-Square	sig	Chi-Square	sig
AO1. The organization has an updated manual of functions and/or procedures according to the needs of the environment and the business.	1.842	.606	135.875	.112
AO2. The jobs are related to their description, analysis and the competences they must develop.	1.205	.752	137.979	.090
AO3. The collaborators know the profile of their cargo (with easy access to the document), their position within the organization, their tasks, powers and managers.	.517	.915	140.089	.072
AO4. The human management area strengthens the institutional philosophy by supporting the internalization of the mission, vision, values and principles; in turn, it is a change manager in the implementation of new processes.	.646	.886	151.452	.018*
AO5. The organization manages mechanisms for employees to propose improvements to jobs or work areas and these in turn are implemented.	5.737	.125	122.725	.340
AO6. Human Management maintains permanent and timely communication with collaborators for the development of processes in the area.	.463	.927	114.007	.561

Organizational aspect	The person in charge of human talent			
	Gender		Age	
	Chi-Square	sig	Chi-Square	sig
AO7. The organization has mechanisms to measure the culture and the organizational climate, in turn developing improvement strategies.	.4585	.205	110.979	.639
AO8. Organizational aspect dimension	26.784	.220	1020.45	.000**

Notes: ** Significant at the 0.01 level; * Significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 2: Perception of the person in charge of human talent labor characteristics with respect to organizational aspects.

Organizational aspect	The person in charge of human talent					
	Salary		Experience		Level Education	
	Chi-Square	sig	Chi-Square	sig	Chi-Square	sig
AO1	11.980	.007**	91.922	.010**	30.561	.032*
AO2	7.557	.056	67.859	.315	19.270	.375
AO3	1.042	.791	85.735	.030*	28.163	.060
AO4	3.226	.358	80.268	.070	22.384	.215
AO5	.870	.833	96.013	.005**	18.403	.429
AO6	5.679	.128	59.065	.617	22.194	.223
AO7	1.470	.689	84.457	.037*	27.812	.065
AO8	30.187	.114	464.592	.457	251.249	.000**

AO1. The organization has an updated manual of functions and/or procedures according to the needs of the environment and the business; AO2. The jobs are related to their description, analysis and the competences they must develop; AO3. The collaborators know the profile of their cargo (with easy access to the document), their position within the organization, their tasks, powers and managers; AO4. The human management area strengthens the institutional philosophy by supporting the internalization of the mission, vision, values and principles; in turn, it is a change manager in the implementation of new processes; AO5. The organization manages mechanisms for employees to propose improvements to jobs or work areas and these in turn are implemented; AO6. Human Management maintains permanent and timely communication with collaborators for the development of processes in the area; AO7. The organization has mechanisms to measure the culture and the organizational climate, in turn developing improvement strategies; AO8. Organizational aspect dimension

Table 3: Descriptive Statistic by Gender and Age.

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Age	N	Mean	SD
AO1. The organization has an updated manual of functions and/or procedures according to the needs of the environment and the business.	Female	106	3.09	.99	18 to 25 years	29	3.06	.99
	Male	69	3.21	.96	26 to 35 years	66	3.00	1.05
					36 to 45 years	43	3.46	.702
					46 to 60 years	37	3.08	1.06
AO2. The jobs are related to their description, analysis and the competences they must develop.	Female	106	3.13	1.00	18 to 25 years	29	3.17	.88
	Male	69	3.23	1.00	26 to 35 years	66	3.01	1.07
					36 to 45 years	43	3.51	.70
					46 to 60 years	37	3.05	1,17
AO3. The collaborators know the profile of their cargo (with easy access to the document), their position within the organization, their tasks, powers and managers.	Female	106	3.30	.87	18 to 25 years	29	3.17	.88
	Male	69	3.33	.90	26 to 35 years	66	3.34	.88
					36 to 45 years	43	3.53	.70
					46 to 60 years	37	3.10	1.02
AO4. The human management area strengthens the institutional philosophy by supporting the internalization of the mission, vision, values and principles; in turn, it is a change manager in the implementation of new processes.	Female	106	2.93	.97	18 to 25 years	29	2.82	1.00
	Male	69	3.02	.98	26 to 35 years	66	3.00	.94
					36 to 45 years	43	3.02	.88
					46 to 60 years	37	2.97	1.14
AO5. The organization manages mechanisms for employees to propose improvements to jobs or work areas and these in turn are	Female	106	3.09	.85	18 to 25 years	29	3.13	.83
	Male	69	3.11	.79	26 to 35 years	66	3.06	.83
					36 to 45 years	43	3.13	.86
					46 to 60 years	37	3.10	.80

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Age	N	Mean	SD
implemented.					years			
AO6. Human Management maintains permanent and timely communication with collaborators for the development of processes in the area.	Female	106	3.35	.79	18 to 25 years	29	3.24	.78
	Male	69	3.31	.83	26 to 35 years	66	3.28	.85
					36 to 45 years	43	3.39	.79
					46 to 60 years	37	3.45	.76
AO7. The organization has mechanisms to measure the culture and the organizational climate, in turn developing improvement strategies.	Female	106	2.94	1.02	18 to 25 years	29	2.58	1.01
	Male	69	2.60	1.07	26 to 35 years	66	2.92	.98
					36 to 45 years	43	2.83	1.06
					46 to 60 years	37	2.75	1.18
AO8. Organizational aspect dimension	Female	106	3.12	.75	18 to 25 years	29	3.03	.71
	Male	69	3.12	.70	26 to 35 years	66	3.09	.75
					36 to 45 years	43	3.27	.56
					46 to 60 years	37	3.07	.87

Table 4: Descriptive Statistic labor characteristics.

	Experie nce (years)	N	Me an	SD	Level education	N	Mea n	SD
AO1. The organization has an updated manual of functions and/or procedures according to the needs of the environment and the business.	1 year or less	53	3.16	.87	primary	2	2.00	1.41
	between 1 and 3	56	2.94	1.05	bachelor	21	2.85	1.01
	between 3 and 5	22	3.5	.85	technical	32	3.15	.91
	between 5 and 10	26	3.26	1.07	technologist	32	2.71	1.08
	more than 10	18	3.05	.99	professional	68	3.35	.89
					specialist	17	3.41	.87
					Magister	3	4.00	.00

	Experi ence (years)	N	Me an	SD	Level education	N	Mea n	SD
AO2. The jobs are related to their description, analysis and the competences they must develop.	1 year or less	53	3.18	.92	primary	2	1.50	.70
	between 1 and 3	56	3.01	1.07	bachelor	21	2.95	1.02
	between 3 and 5	22	3.40	.85	technical	32	3.18	.96
	between 5 and 10	26	3.30	1.04	technologist	32	2.93	1.07
	more than 10	18	3.11	1.13	professional	68	3.30	.96
					specialist	17	3.35	.93
					Magister	3	4.00	.00
AO3. The collaborators know the profile of their cargo (with easy access to the document), their position within the organization, their tasks, powers and managers.	1 year or less	53	3.33	.83	primary	2	2.00	1.41
	between 1 and 3	56	3.16	.98	bachelor	21	3.28	.84
	between 3 and 5	22	3.59	.59	technical	32	3.31	.89
	between 5 and 10	26	3.42	.85	technologist	32	3.12	1.03
	more than 10	18	3.22	1.00	professional	68	3.42	.75
					specialist	17	3.29	.98
					Magister	3	4.00	.00
AO4. The human management area strengthens the institutional philosophy by supporting the internalization of the mission, vision, values and principles; in turn, it is a change manager in the implementation of new processes.	1 year or less	53	2.84	.90	primary	2	2.50	2.12
	between 1 and 3	56	2.91	.99	bachelor	21	2.61	.97
	between 3 and 5	22	3.31	.89	technical	32	2.90	1.02
	between 5 and 10	26	3.03	1.03	technologist	32	2.87	1.07
	more than 10	18	3.00	1.13	professional	68	3.14	.86
					specialist	17	2.88	.99
					Magister	3	4.00	.00
AO5. The organization manages	1 year or less	53	2.98	.77	primary	2	2.50	.70
	between	5	3.0	.85	bachelor	2	2.85	.91

	Experi ence (years)	N	Me an	SD	Level education	N	Mea n	SD
mechanisms for employees to propose improvements to jobs or work areas and these in turn are implemented.	1 and 3	6	3			1		
	between 3 and 5	2	3.4		technical	3	3.00	
		2	5	.73		2		.71
	between 5 and 10	2	3.3		technologist	3	3.15	
		6	3.3	.78		2		.88
	more than 10	1	2.9		professional	6	3.19	
	8	4	.99		8		.85	
					specialist	1	3.11	
						7		.78
					Magister	3	3.66	
						2		.57
AO6. Human Management maintains permanent and timely communication with collaborators for the development of processes in the area.	1 year or less	5	3.2		primary	2	2.50	
		3	6	.83				.70
	between 1 and 3	5	3.3		bachelor	2	3.00	
		6	0	.80		1		.89
	between 3 and 5	2	3.5		technical	3	3.25	
		2	9	.66		2		.84
between 5 and 10	2	3.3		technologist	3	3.18		
	6	0	.92		2		.96	
more than 10	1	3.4		professional	6	3.50		
	8	4	.70		8		.68	
					specialist	1	3.58	
						7		.61
					Magister	3	4.00	
								.00
AO7. The organization has mechanisms to measure the culture and the organizational climate, in turn developing improvement strategies.	1 year or less	5	2.6		primary	2	1.00	
		3	4	1.02				.00
	between 1 and 3	5	2.8		bachelor	2	2.47	
		6	0	.99		1		1.2
	between 3 and 5	2	3.0		technical	3	2.71	
		2	0	1.15		2		1.0
between 5 and 10	2	2.9		technologist	3	2.65		
	6	6	.99		2		1.0	
more than 10	1	2.8		professional	6	3.04		
	8	8	1.27		8		.93	
					specialist	1	2.94	
						7		1.0
					Magister	3	3.00	
								1.7
								3
AO8. Organizational aspect dimension	1 year or less	5	3.0		primary	2	2.00	
		3	6	.63				1.0
	between 1 and 3	5	3.0		bachelor	2	2.86	
	6	2	.78		1		.70	
between	2	3.4		technical	3	3.07		
			.65				.71	

	Experience (years)	N	Mean	SD	Level education	N	Mean	SD
	3 and 5	2	0			2		
	between 5 and 10	26	3.23	.79	technologist	32	2.95	.83
	more than 10	18	3.09	.82	professional	68	3.28	.66
					specialist	17	3.22	.71
					Magister	3	3.81	.32

Table 5 : Descriptive Statistics salary.

	Salary ^a	N	Mean	SD
AO1. The organization has an updated manual of functions and/or procedures according to the needs of the environment and the business.	less than 500 dollars	72	3.30	1.01
	500 dollars or more	103	3.02	.94
AO2. The jobs are related to their description, analysis and the competences they must develop.	less than 500 dollars	72	3.27	1.03
	500 dollars or more	103	3.09	.97
AO3. The collaborators know the profile of their cargo (with easy access to the document), their position within the organization, their tasks, powers and managers.	less than 500 dollars	72	3.33	.90
	500 dollars or more	103	3.30	.87
AO4. The human management area strengthens the institutional philosophy by supporting the internalization of the mission, vision, values and principles; in turn, it is a change manager in the implementation of new processes.	less than 500 dollars	72	3.06	.98
	500 dollars or more	103	2.90	.97
AO5. The organization manages mechanisms for employees to propose improvements to jobs or work areas and these in turn are implemented.	less than 500 dollars	72	3.15	.79
	500 dollars or more	103	3.06	.85
AO6. Human Management maintains permanent and timely communication with collaborators for the development of processes in the area.	less than 500 dollars	72	3.52	.67
	500 dollars or more	103	3.21	.87
AO7. The organization has mechanisms to measure the culture and the organizational climate, in turn developing improvement strategies.	less than 500 dollars	72	2.80	1.10
	500 dollars or more	103	2.81	1.01

	Salary ^a	N	Mean	SD
AO8. Organizational aspect dimension	less than 500 dollars	72	3.21	.75
	500 dollars or more	103	3.06	.71

^aFor the conversion of Colombian pesos to dollars, the average of the representative exchange rate of the TRM market in 2019 was used, Source: Superintendencia Financiera de Colombia (www.superfinanciera.gov.co)

Table 6 : Organizational aspects and human management practices.

	R	SP	I	T	PE	SA	C	LW	HSW	CM
AO1	.309**	.259**	.360**	.377**	.355**	.378**	.181*	.250**	.417**	.304**
AO2	.355**	.269**	.277**	.343**	.395**	.381**	.172*	.256**	.342**	.259**
AO3	.366**	.318**	.329**	.308**	.368**	.303**	0,058	.186*	.238**	.207**
AO4	.262**	.260**	.315**	.432**	.389**	.319**	.182*	.304**	.303**	.273**
AO5	.308**	.298**	.291**	.262**	.325**	.287**	.248**	.329**	.247**	.240**
AO6	.277**	.302**	.302**	.308**	.322**	.237**	.177*	.286**	.248**	.220**
AO7	.339**	.381**	.288**	.345**	.420**	.227**	0,127	.319**	.211**	.328**
AO8	.403**	.379**	.392**	.435**	.471**	.389**	.207**	.351**	.366**	.336**

R-Recruitment, SP-Staff pick, I-Induction, T-Training, PE-Performance evaluation, SA-Staff Administration, C-Compensations (wages, increases and incentives), LW-Labor well-being, HSW-Health and Safety at Work, CM-Competency Model

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

1. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Respondents are the people responsible for human talent in SME companies. Villavicencio is the capital city of the Meta department in Colombia.

Data were collected using the 4 Likert scale questionnaire (mp10). The questionnaire was distributed among SME companies in the tertiary sector of the Villavicencio city. A sample of 176 people was obtained, tabulated and analyzed using the IBM SPSS 25 statistic with the mean and standard deviation, to analyze the descriptive statistics (see Table 3,4,5).

The differences in responses among the respondents were explored referring to their characteristics when observing the chi-square value to justify the importance of the differences (Table 1 and 2). Then the Pearson correlation was used to produce a correlation matrix between organizational aspects and human management practices. It can be seen in Table 6. Correlation data supports the relationship, interpretation and support in the data analysis.

1. CONCLUSIONS:

It is observed that there are no significant differences in gender with respect to organizational aspects, but in terms of age, there is a significant difference. In terms of manual functions and

procedures according to the needs of the business in terms of salary, experience and education there is a significant difference between groups.

In relation issues, it was found that when SME companies develop the elements of organizational aspects, there is a positive relationship with human management practices, which is paid to the organization in productivity.

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